

EH DEN

EUROPEAN HEALTH DATA & EVIDENCE NETWORK

806968 – EH DEN

European Health Data & Evidence Network

WP4 – Technical Implementations

D4.3 Yearly Progress Report on Technical Framework

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DOCUMENT HISTORY

Version	Date	Description
V1	15 Nov 2019	First Draft
V2	28 Nov 2019	Reviewed version
V2final	20 Dec 2019	Final version after consortium review

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DEFINITIONS

Participants of the EHDEN Consortium are referred to herein according to the following codes:

EMC	Erasmus Universitair Medisch Centrum Rotterdam- The Netherlands (Project Coordinator)
Synapse	Synapse Research Management Partners S.L. - Spain
UOXF	The Chancellor, Masters and Scholars of the University of Oxford - United Kingdom
UTARTU	Tartu Ulikool - Estonia
UAVR	Universidade de Aveiro – Portugal
The Hyve	The Hyve BV – the Netherlands
Odysseus	Odysseus Data Services SRO – Czech Republic
EPF	Forum Europeen des Patients (FPE) - Luxembourg
NICE	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence – United Kingdom
UMC	Stiftelsen WHO Collaborating Centre for International Drug Monitoring - Sweden
ICHOM	International Consortium for Health Outcomes measurement LTD - United Kingdom
Janssen	Janssen Pharmaceutica NV - Belgium (Project Lead)
Pfizer	Pfizer Limited – United Kingdom
Abbvie	AbbVie Inc - United States
IRIS	Institut De Recherches Internationales Servier - France
SARD	Sanofi Aventis Recherche & Developement - France
Bayer	Bayer Aktiengesellschaft - Germany
Lilly	Eli Lilly and Company Limited – United Kingdom
AZ	AstraZeneca AB - Sweden
Novartis	Novartis Pharma AG - Switzerland
UCB	UCB Biopharma SPRL - Belgium
Celgene	Celgene Management SARL - Switzerland

Grant agreement	The agreement signed between the beneficiaries and the IMI JU for the undertaking of the EHDEN project (806968).
Project	The sum of all activities carried out in the framework of the Grant Agreement.
Consortium	The EHDEN Consortium, comprising the above-mentioned legal entities.
Consortium agreement	Agreement concluded amongst EHDEN participants for the implementation of the Grant Agreement. Such an agreement shall not affect the parties' obligations to the Community and/or to one another arising from the Grant Agreement.

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

The EHDEN technical framework (see deliverable D4.1) saw significant progress during its first year across all constituting components. The foundation was laid in a series of workshops that culminated in Deliverable D4.1 Technical Framework Design and Architecture. Subsequently, progress was made across all defined components, in particular – but not limited to- the database^[OBJ], Arachne federated network application, the ETL tooling, the Data Quality Dashboard and a first step towards an integrated security layer. Specific attention was also prepared to provide and integrate documentation. A working prototype of the main applications is available for testing purposes under <http://test.ehden.eu>. <https://www.academy.ehden.eu>. A working prototype of the main applications is available for testing purposes under <http://test.ehden.eu>.

This deliverable summarizes the progress on the technical framework in year 1, for more details we refer to D4.1 Technical Framework Design and Architecture.

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1. INTRODUCTION

EHDEN aims to make health data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR). As most health data cannot be freely shared, the approach uses a federated network of health data sources. The analyses are sent to the data sites, collecting aggregated results.

This requires tools and technical solutions, e.g., a database catalogue to find the data, a tool to execute analytical code against standardised data, etc. Furthermore, tools are needed to train our stakeholders. The technical framework brings together all tools within one eco-system. During the first year of the EHDEN project, the focus was on defining a single technology architecture in which the different applications are represented. The EHDEN architecture is composed of multiple stand-alone applications, both existing open source OHDSI tools and tools developed specifically within EHDEN, which we aim to bring together under the EHDEN Portal. This makes the applications easily accessible for EHDEN collaborators and enables e.g. shared user and access rights management & security. Ultimately, the EHDEN framework should enable –through a set of applications- to support the end-to-end business process flow from data discovery through study execution through to results (evidence).

For development of the applications, we collaborate intensively with the global open source OHDSI community. We aim to involve the OHDSI community in the tools that are relevant for both groups. This collaboration has many benefits; we can avoid duplication of effort, we can build further on existing applications, we can rely on help and feedback from many skilled people, and most importantly, it allows our efforts to be maintained and further developed after the EHDEN project.

In this yearly progress report, we summarize the work done in the first year of the project. For more details we refer to D4.1 Technical Framework Design and Architecture.

2. APPLICATIONS

2.1. EHDEN Portal

The EHDEN Portal is the main tool through which all the tools in the EHDEN ecosystem can be accessed. It is based on a content management system that allows linkage to the different underlying applications. The portal is online, accessible at <https://portal.ehden.eu/>. During the first year of EHDEN a first version of the architecture was implemented and deployed. The platform links to the Database Catalogue, the EHDEN Academy, ATLAS and Arachne and integrates the Elixir AAI (Elixir Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure).

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2.2. Database Catalogue

The Database Catalogue is the primary entry point for data discovery within EHDEN as it exposes metadata about the participating data sources. A first version of the Catalogue was deployed and can be accessed through the EHDEN Portal. In the Database Catalogue data sources are characterized based on a schema that can be easily defined by data partners based on the metadata attributes that best characterize their data. A first draft of the schema template was designed and is currently in place in the Database Catalogue.

2.3. OHDSI Atlas

Atlas versions 2.7.0 through to 2.7.4 were released during the first year of EHDEN. Releases focused on improving the user experience and expanding capabilities of data source (characterization), vocabulary search, concept set definitions, cohort definition and characterisation, cohort pathways, incidence rates, population level effect estimation, prediction models and the security setup.

The current ATLAS 2.7.41 is a stable and secure release which has been deployed at most of the OHDSI Network sites. The tool underwent a full security and vulnerability scan. Most recent work focused on authentication integration with major Identity Providers.

2.4. OHDSI Arachne

Arachne implements a technical solution for federated study execution in the EHDEN data network. A researcher can send analytical code to data custodians, who can execute this against their CDM, and can return the results of the study.

Arachne version 1.15.0² has been released over the past EHDEN year. This release supports a full integration with Atlas allowing users to import and execute Atlas analyses including cohort counts and characterisations,

¹ <https://github.com/OHDSI/Atlas/releases/tag/v2.7.4>

² <https://github.com/OHDSI/ArachneUI/releases/tag/1.15.0>

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incidence rates, population level effect estimation and patient prediction models on federated OMOP-CDM databases.

Arachne now accommodates custom-defined analyses in SQL and R. Local analysis is also enabled in version 1.15.0: Data Node allows for local analysis execution in standalone mode (SQL and R)

Currently, work is being done to integrate Arachne with EHDEN Database Catalogue and Elixir. This focuses on Account and Authentication Management and ISP integration on the EHDEN/OHDSI platform.

2.5. OHDSI Athena and Standardised Vocabularies

The list of vocabularies that are now part of the OMOP common data model which will be used to standardize the participating data sources, has increased significantly over the past year. New additions and extensions³ include:

- NAACCR (oncology)
- HemOnc (oncology)
- ATC (classification)
- SNOMED veterinary
- OSM
- US Census
- RxNORM extension with different European drug vocabulary extensions

2.6. Tantalus

A new tool – Tantalus⁴ – has been developed to compare different versions of the vocabulary. The tool executes multiple checks, e.g., domain changes, concept mapping changes. It provides a Shiny application to visually inspect row level differences between the vocabularies. The tool is easily customizable, i.e. new checks can be added by including new comparison queries and the Shiny application will expose the results without additional code effort.

³ <https://github.com/OHDSI/Vocabulary-v5.0/releases>

⁴ <https://github.com/EHDEN/Tantalus>

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Tantulus

Home | Tabular | Summary | Feedback

Tantulus

Introduction

Welcome to TANTALUS.

TANTALUS is an open source application developed as a part of OHDSI intended to help expose differences between two vocabulary versions.

The data is generated using the [Tantulus R Package](#)

The following comparison queries are currently available:

ID	Description
9.01	Concept name changed
10.01	Concept domain changed
99.01	Source concepts with new standard mappings, including 0

In **tabular** view you can select the results for the following aggregation levels: description, domain, or vocabulary.

After selecting an aggregation key, you can filter the results table by clicking on the rows in the table that is generated. Additional filtering and search options are available per column on the top of the table and overall on top of the page.

There is an option to download the results (those that are in view as defined by the "entries") as csv or excel file.

In the **summary** view you can find an overview of aggregated results of the comparison.

Note you can remove the side bar if more space is needed using the button in the header.

Getting Involved

2.7. Query Library Tool

The newly developed Query Library⁵ provides access to over 200 predefined queries that could be run against datasources in the OMOP CDM format. These queries are put in an extensible framework. It includes queries against the OMOP vocabulary as well as the OMOP CDM clinical domains. A local installation of the tool allows direct execution of the queries on a local OMOP database. This library will be used to train SME's and data sources to work with OMOP CDM data.

As this tool has use in the wider OHDSI community, it is currently maintained and hosted by the OHDSI community. A pilot version is available at <http://data.ohdsi.org/QueryLibrary/>.

QueryLibrary

Home | Configuration | Feedback

Search:

Select a query

Column visibility Show 10 entries

Group	Name
All	All
care site	CS01 Care site place of service counts
care site	CS02 Patient count per care site place of service.
condition era	CE01 Min/max/average length of condition
condition era	CE02 Age/gender of patients with condition
condition era	CE03 Min/max, average length of condition stratified by age/gender
condition era	CE04 Conditions, stratified by year, age group and gender
condition era	CE05 Conditions that are seasonally dependent
condition era	CE06 Conditions most likely to result in death
condition era	CE07 Comorbidities of patient with condition
condition era	CE08 Number of comorbidity for patients with condition

Showing 1 to 10 of 202 entries

Previous 1 2 3 4 5 ... 21 Next

Query Description

CS02: Patient count per care site place of service.

Description

This query is used to count patients per care site place of service.

Query

```

SELECT
  cs.place_of_service_concept_id,
  COUNT(*) AS num_patients
FROM
  cdm.care_site AS cs
JOIN
  cdm.person AS p ON p.care_site_id = cs.care_site_id
GROUP BY
  cs.place_of_service_concept_id
ORDER BY
  cs.place_of_service_concept_id
;

```

Input

None

Output

⁵ <https://github.com/EHDEN/QueryLibrary>

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2.8. ETL Tooling

The OHDSI ETL tooling support the SME's and data sources to create the transformation scripts. The main functionalities are profiling the source data (White Rabbit), creating mapping documentation (Rabbit in a Hat) and mapping source terms to the OMOP standard vocabulary (Usagi).

In the first year both White Rabbit and Rabbit in a Hat were further developed to extend the functionality of the tool. Notable new features are the generation of documentation as markup / html, supporting OMOP CDM version 6.0, reporting the number of unique values per field and generation of a SQL skeleton. In addition, numerous small bug fixes and improvements were made.

2.9. Data Quality Dashboard

The Data Quality Dashboard⁶ offers in its first release an overview of the results of a predefined set of data quality checks on a particular database in the OMOP CDM format. The tool is the results of an OHDSI workgroup and a demo is available at <https://data.ohdsi.org/DataQualityDashboard/>. An in depth description of this new tool is given in deliverable D4.2, which is currently under review.

DATA QUALITY ASSESSMENT

SYNTHEA SYNTHETIC HEALTH DATABASE

Results generated at 2019-08-22 14:15:06 in 29 mins

	Verification				Validation				Total			
	Pass	Fail	Total	% Pass	Pass	Fail	Total	% Pass	Pass	Fail	Total	% Pass
Plausibility	159	21	180	88%	283	0	283	100%	442	21	463	95%
Conformance	637	34	671	95%	104	0	104	100%	741	34	775	96%
Completeness	369	17	386	96%	5	10	15	33%	374	27	401	93%
Total	1165	72	1237	94%	392	10	402	98%	1557	82	1639	95%

2.10. Security

A security policy for EHDEN was drafted on basis of the ISO 27001 information security standard. This policy defines the security scope, objectives, roles, data policy etc. However, several questions in the policy are still open for further discussions and the policy will be updated throughout the project lifetime. Initial brainstorming has been carried out for identifying potential risks for EHDEN information security.

An important part of the security is the trusted authentication and authorisation mechanism of the users. To enable that, we have made a full cooperation with Elixir project, and Elixir AAI (Elixir Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure) which has successfully been integrated with the EHDEN data catalogue.

⁶ <https://github.com/OHDSI/DataQualityDashboard>

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3. CONCLUSION

In year 1, a blueprint for the EHDEN technical architecture was developed (D4.1). This specific deliverable focuses on the progress that has been made towards realising this architecture during the first year of EHDEN. Leveraging and synchronisation with the OHDSI initiative has proven to be a critical element in this and progress on OHDSI has benefited EHDEN and also the inverse holds true. All components that are part of the EHDEN architecture had one or more releases during the past year and the core components have been made part of a demo environment.

For year 2 and beyond, the focus will be on strengthening the seamless integration of the different components with clear API's and further expansion of the integrated security system. In addition, the individual components as well as the overall integration between these components will be subject to further refinement and testing on basis of the use case development that will happen in WP1 through WP3.